

Preparation and Characterization of High Strength and High Oil Resistant Flame Retardant EVA Composites for Cable

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Background & Motivation

The application of ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer (EVA) is seriously restricted by the characteristics of flammability. It is generally carried out by using inorganic hydroxide to implement flame retardant modification. Filler dispersion and the polymer-filler interfacial bonding are two critical factors. Macromolecular compatibilizer is mainly used in polymer-filler composites. Therefore, we use magnesium hydroxide (MH) and aluminum hydroxide (ATH) to modify the EVA with a glycidyl methacrylate functionalized polymer (POE-g-GMA). The influences of POE-g-GMA on morphology, thermal stability, crystallization behavior and rheological property were investigated.

■ The structure of EVA and POE-g-GMA

■ Formulation of EVA composites containing different content of POE-g-GMA.

	Sample1	Sample2	Sample3	Sample4	sample5
EVA(VA28%)	24%	23%	21%	19%	17%
EVA(VA40%)	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%
POE-g-GMA	0%	1%	3%	5%	7%
FRC	46%	45%	46%	46%	46%
SiO ₂	7%	7%	7%	7%	7%
DCP	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%	2.5%
TAIC	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%	0.5%
Other additives	10%	10%	10%	10%	10%

Micromorphology Analysis

■ POE-g-GMA was beneficial to enhance the interaction force between the filler and polymer matrix.

Thermal Properties

■ DSC results were ascribed to the weakened ordering ability of EVA molecular chain with the introduction of POE-g-GMA, which results in the difficulty of forming a macroscopic ordered structure with good regularity of the amorphous region.

Rheological Behavior & Mechanical Properties

■ A type of solidlike behavior occurred owing to the formation of filler network especially when the filler content is high.

■ The tensile properties and oil resistance of EVA composites.

Sample	unit	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
T.S	MPa	11.9	12.1	12.6	13.3	13.9
E.B	%	160	165	179	162	177
change of T.S(oil)	%	-18	-19	-19	-12	-13
change of E.B(oil)	%	-15	-14	-15	-10	-9

Conclusions

- POE-g-GMA could significantly improve the dispersion of the filler in the matrix and enhance the interfacial adhesion between the two.
- POE-g-GMA could improve the thermal stability of composite materials, mainly due to the increase of initial decomposition temperature.
- The solid cross-linking network was formed inside the composites, and the interface structure tends to be perfect. Therefore, the tensile strength and the solvent resistance both were improved.

References

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